

Transmission of RTBV, RTSV, and RTBV +RTSV on IR54, IR36, and TN1 by GLH, area of acidic and basic honeydew excreted during inoculation feeding, and survival of GLH on the respective cultivars. IRRI, 1986.

Koronadal, South Cotabato, and reared on TN1 for 5-6 overlapping generations was used in this study. About 3-4 d after molting, adult GLH were given 4-d acquisition access to plants infected with both rice tungro bacilliform (RTBV) and rice tungro spherical viruses (RTSV). The GLH then were tested individually on IR36, IR54, and TN1 for virus transmission, feeding behavior during inoculation feeding, and survival on seedlings.

Feeding behavior was monitored by the reaction of honeydew spots on bromocresol-green treated filter paper discs. Blue color spots (basic honeydew) indicates phloem feeding and orange or brown color spots (acidic honeydew) indicates xylem feeding. Inoculated plants were indexed by latex serology. After inoculation feeding, each GLH was caged on about 3-wk-old plants of the respective cultivars to determine life span.

Leafhoppers fed on both phloem and xylem on all test varieties. They excreted less basic honeydew on GLH-resistant IR36 and IR54, survived fewer days, and transmitted viruses at lower rates (see figure). On susceptible TN1, the GLH excreted more basic honeydew, survived longer, and transmitted viruses at higher rates.

There was a significant correlation between percent virus transmission and, the average areas of basic honeydew spots, and the average life span of GLH on the test varieties. However, there was

Transmission of RTBV and RTSV on 3 cultivars by individual GLH and their feeding behavior during inoculation access.^a IRRI, 1987.

Cultivar	GLH tested (no.)	Transmissions (no.) by GLH	GLH (no.) that fed on			
			Phloem	Phloem and xylem	Xylem	
IR36	30	RTBV+RTSV	10	0	7	3
		RTBV	7	0	5	2
		RTSV	1	0	1	0
		None	12	0	1	11
IR54	30	RTBV+RTSV	3	0	2	1
		RTBV	9	0	2	7
		RTSV	0	0	0	0
		None	18	0	3	15
TN1	30	RTBV+RTSV	18	0	16	2
		RTBV	6	0	6	0
		RTSV	2	1	1	0
		None	4	0	2	2

^aGLH fed on plants infected with RTBV and RTSV were individually given a 1-d inoculation access feeding on seedlings.

no correlation between the areas of basic honeydew spots excreted by the individual leafhoppers during inoculation feeding and life span on the same variety.

On IR54, there was no clear tendency indicating that GLH which predominantly excreted more basic honeydew transmitted the viruses at higher rate. But on IR36 and TN1, GLH which excreted more basic honeydew transmitted the viruses. Irrespective of variety, a high proportion of GLH which fed on both phloem and xylem transmitted the viruses. About one-third of the GLH that fed on xylem alone transmitted the viruses.

The results indicate that virus transmission occurs even when GLH feed predominantly on xylem.

Incidence of rice panicle stalk blast (BI) in Manipur

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Internodal culm BI of rice was found for the first time in experimental plots of MAC and in many rice-growing areas in Manipur in 1985; the incidence was severe in 1986.

Punshi and KD 2-6-3, varieties widely cultivated in Manipur, suffered 60-100% yield loss.

The disease attacked rice plants from anthesis on. Symptoms were numerous white, empty panicles. But the

uppermost leaf sheath enclosing the infected internode remained healthy. Sections of tissues of the uppermost internode rotted and were covered with sooty spore masses. In late infection, grains developed poorly. The disease was more severe in dry fields than in wet

fields.

When microscopically examined, diseased samples collected from different rice-growing valley areas in the State consistently showed *Pyricularia oryzae* Cav. The pathogen was isolated on rice straw extract agar medium and its

pathogenicity proved.

The sudden spread of the disease seems to have been influenced by cultivation of high-yielding, susceptible rice varieties and by a long dry spell during late growth stage. □

Pest Control and Management

INSECTS

Predators of rice insect pests in Chhattishgarh region, Madhya Pradesh, India

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Madhya Pradesh is situated between latitude 17° and 26°N and longitude 74° and 84°E. Rice is the predominant crop in Chhattishgarh, which has mixed red and yellow soil, 1,400-1,600 mm average rainfall, 85-95% average humidity, and

Predators of rice insect pests in Chhattishgarh region, Madhya Pradesh, India, 1984-86.

Predators	Prevalence
I Araneida	
Tetragnathidae	High
<i>Tetragnatha mandibulata</i>	
Lycosidae	
<i>Lycosa pseudoannulata</i>	Moderate
II Orthoptera	
Tettigoniidae	
<i>Conocephalus longipennis</i>	Moderate
III Odonota	
Coenagrionidae	
<i>Ischnura</i> sp.	Low
<i>Agriocnemis pygmaea</i>	High
IV Coleoptera	
Carabidae	Moderate
<i>Ophionea nigrofasciata</i>	
<i>Casnoidae indica</i>	Low
Coccinellidae	
<i>Coccinella arcuata</i>	Moderate
<i>Menochilus sexmaculata</i>	Low
<i>Scymnus postpinctus</i>	Low
Staphylinidae	
<i>Paederus fuscipes</i>	High
V Hemiptera	
Miridae	High
<i>Cyrtorhinus lividipennis</i>	
Gerridae	Moderate
<i>Limnogonus</i> sp.	
<i>Microvelia</i> sp.	Moderate
Nabidae	
<i>Tropiconabis capsiformis</i>	Moderate

20-30 °C temperature during the Jun-Sep monsoon. Monsoon rice cultivation favors insect multiplication.

We counted natural enemies of monsoon rice pests in 1984-86 (see table). □

Effect of insecticides on eggs of *Brevennia rehi* (Lindinger)

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We tested the ovicidal action of 11 insecticides in the laboratory (see table).

For each treatment, 50 eggs were

placed in a petri dish lined with moist filter paper and sprayed with 1 ml spray solution, using an atomizer.

Eggs that hatched were counted every 15 min for 3 d. Data were converted into arc sin values and corrected for natural mortality using Abbott's formula.

BPMC 0.25 kg ai/ha delayed hatching most, and crawlers that hatched, died. □

Effect of insecticides on hatchability of *B. rehi* eggs.^a Coimbatore, India.

Insecticide	Rate (kg ai/ha)	Hatchability (%)	Mortality (%)
Endosulfan	0.33	11 def	31 de
Phosphamidon	0.25	13 efg	22 f
Monocrotophos	0.20	10 def	36 de
Fenthion	0.50	11 cde	34 de
Chlorpyrifos	0.35	12 efg	22 f
Methyl demeton	0.125	10 c	39 d
Dimethoate	0.15	8 cd	51 c
Phosalone	0.35	12 efg	23 f
Biphenyl methyl carbamate	0.25	2 a	88 a
Deltamethrin	0.01	14 fg	14 g
Carbaryl	0.5	7 b	58 b
Control	-	14 g	-

^a Mean of 3 replications. Figures in parentheses are arc sin transformed values. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different (P = 0.05) by DMRT.

Insect pests on main and ratoon rice

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Intan, a popular irrigated rice variety in the hilly region of Karnataka, was sown 5 Jul 1984 and 7 Jun 1985 in 8- × 1- ×

0.1-m nursery beds. Seedlings were transplanted 2 Aug 1984 in 64-m² plots and 13 Jul 1985 in 66-m² plots with 4 replications.

To supplement natural buildup of insect population, 15-20 20-m-long rows were maintained on each side of the experimental field. No insecticides were